

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF VERB PHRASES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГЛАГОЛЬНЫХ СЛОВСОЧЕТАНИЙ В
УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA FE'L SO'Z TURKUMINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

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Abstract: *This article examines structural discordances in English and Uzbek by providing specific examples of differences and similarities between the two languages. We will study how to employ grammatical categories of verbs in both languages in this post [1].*

Keywords: *English, Uzbek, verb, suffixes, order, numeral, nouns, grammatical transformation, syntactical structures, pronouns, article, gender, tenses and other grammatical categories.*

Аннотация: *В этой статье исследуются структурные несоответствия в английском и узбекском языках, приводятся конкретные примеры различий и сходств между двумя языками. В этом посте мы изучим, как использовать грамматические категории глаголов в обоих языках [1].*

Ключевые слова: *английский, узбекский, глагол, суффиксы, порядок, числительное, существительные, грамматические преобразования, синтаксические конструкции, местоимения, артикль, род, времена и другие грамматические категории.*

INTRODUCTION. We already know that declarative statements in English have the following structure: Subject – Predicate – Object. As for Uzbek sentences, they are formed due to another scheme: Subject – Object – Predicate (at the end of a sentence). As a result, the word order of English and Uzbek phrases diverge drastically. Furthermore, suffixes such as -ni and -ini are frequently used in Uzbek phrases. Three types of structural discordances in English and Uzbek set expressions can be identified: 1. Complete conformity. 2. Partial conformity. 3. Complete discordance [2].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. The term "complete structural concordance" refers to the alignment of structures, word combinations, and parts of speech in both English

and Uzbek. Consider the number category, which is similar in both languages: I would like to express my viewpoint – Men fikrimni aytmoqchiman I would like to express my viewpoints – Men fikrlarimni aytmoqchiman Let me introduce my friend – Do‘stimni tanishtirishga ijozat bering. Let me introduce my friends – Do‘stlarimni tanishtirishga ijozat bering.

However, the word order in these phrases is different: in English phrases, the predicate comes after the subject, whereas in Uzbek phrases, the predicate comes after the subject and object. There are extremely few examples of English and Uzbek speech formulations that are structurally identical. Typically, such expressions have two or three parts: an international telegram – xalqaro telegramma travelers’ check – sayohatchilar cheki [3-4].

Partially discordant categories include tense, voice, and case. There are two cases in English, and six in Uzbek. I heard much about your country – Sizning mamlakatingiz to‘g‘risida ko‘p eshitganman. Two English words –your country are rendered by one Uzbek word –mamlakatingiz. Moreover, they vary from the viewpoint of category of cases. Another example: We are from Tashkent – Biz Toshkentdanmiz. As we see, three English lexemes –are from Tashkent|| are combined in one Uzbek lexeme –Toshkentdanmiz. We came here on the invitation of the government of – Biz hukumati taklifiga binoan keldik. In this example the structure of the English expression –on the invitation of government|| is different by word order in the Uzbek equivalent –hukumati taklifiga (word order is vice versa).

As we see in the examples above, set expressions with partial accordance are similar in meaning but differ in structure: one letter – bitta kitob five letters – beshta kitob [5- 6]. As we see, English phrases consist of numeral and noun (singular and plural), but Uzbek phrases consist of numeral and noun in singular. Even in cases of total semantic accordance there may be revealed cases of partial structural discordance: a list of items – molar ro‘yhati (word order differs + Uzbek suffix –i|| in the word –ro‘yhati||) customs restrictions – bojhona cheklovlari (same word order but Uzbek suffix –i|| in the word –cheklovlari|| import license – import uchun ruhsatnoma (same word order + Uzbek postposition –uchun||). Total structural discordance is first of all vivid in the category of possession which is expressed by possessive suffixes in Uzbek and by possessive pronouns in English:

possessive pronouns in English:

May I introduce you to my family? – Sizni oilamga tanishtirishga ruhsat bering. This is your invitation, please. – Marhamat, sizning taklifnomangiz [7].

So, on these common examples we can confirm that a communicant of English-Uzbek conversation should master all possessive pronouns of English and possessive suffixes (endings) of Uzbek. Total grammatical discordance is vivid also on the use of

English articles which don't exist in the Uzbek language system but sometimes can be rendered with the help of another lexical means:

I would like to present you with the gift – Men sizga mana bu sovg'ani topshirmoqchi edim. In the Uzbek variant the English definite article –the|| is transferred by the Uzbek demonstrative pronouns –mana bu||. What a lovely surprise! – Qanday ajoyib uchrashuv! In this Uzbek set expression there is no rendering of the English article –a||. The most vivid examples of total structural discordances can be demonstrated on the material of English and Uzbek set expressions which have the form of sentence: It is I who should thank you – Sizga minnatdorchilik bildirishim kerak I'm terribly sorry – Meni afv eting It is just the other way round – Aksincha As the examples show, meaning and communicative aim of informing or rendering definite information, desire, point of view or feeling towards something is identical in both languages but their grammatical structures are totally different [8-9].

Result and discussion for rendering the meaningful content of speech formulas from one language into another, we apply various types of grammatical transformation: change of word order, omitting some words, adding word(s), conversion of parts of speech and others. One of the most frequently used types of grammatical transformation is change of word order, i.e. change of position of parts of speech. Please, accept my sincerest wishes on your birthday – Tug'ilgan kuningizda mening samimiy tilaklarimni qabul qiling. In these examples we come across with change of structure: in the English variant the reason of congratulation is shown in the second part of the sentence, as for the Uzbek sentence, the reason comes at the very beginning of the sentence. Moreover, English –please|| is omitted in Uzbek because its meaning is rendered by other components of the sentence. Another example of change of word order: I wish you speedy recovery – Tezda sog'ayib ketishingizni tilayman [10]. Besides change of word order in these examples we come across with conversion of parts of speech: in English the phrase –speedy recovery|| is expressed by adjective + noun, as for Uzbek –tezda sog'ayib ketishingizni|| is expressed by adverb + verb. He is a good speaker – U yahshi gapiradi. As it is clear, English –good speaker|| is expressed by an adjective + noun, in Uzbek we have –yahshi gapiradi|| – adverb + verb. I wish you good luck – Sizga omad tilayman. Here we have omitting of the personal pronoun –I|| but its meaning is rendered by suffix –-man|| in the verb –tilayman||. Omitting often takes place in Uzbek variants of conveying the meaning of English sentences with –that||: He said that he would be glad to see us – U bizlarni ko'rsa hursand bo'lishini aytdi. As we see the meaning of the sentence is rendered by another linguistic means. He said his opinion – U fikrini aytdi. In Uzbek sentence –his|| is omitted because it is rendered by suffix –-ini|| in the word.

The English article –a|| is transferred by the Uzbek indefinite pronoun –qandaydir|| (someone). In the sentence –She will come in an hour|| the article –an||

points at number (one hour), so in Uzbek we'll have –U bir soatda keladi||. So, English article –an|| is rendered by Uzbek numeral –one||. Many cases of structural discordance are based on inversion. It is natural because English sentences are formed on Subject + Predicate structure. In Uzbek sentences predicate is placed at the very end: I beg your pardon – Sizdan uzr so'rayman [12]. I can't agree with you – Fikringizga qo'shila olmayman. If you want to know my opinion – Mening fikrimni bilmoqchi bo'lsangiz. Sometimes inversion of parts of speech takes place in English-Uzbek sentences: The last week saw an intensification of diplomatic activity. – O'tgan haftada diplomatic munosabatlarning faollashuvi kuzatildi. English –last week|| is used as the subject of the sentence, but in the Uzbek sentence –o'tgan haftada|| is adverbial modifier of place. Another difficulty in English-Uzbek speech act is rendering the category of gender which is easily expressed by pronouns –he||, –she||, –his||, –her||, –him|| in the English language. In Uzbek the system of pronouns doesn't contain those which are able to express gender: She is from England – U (kishi) Angliyadan. He is from Switzerland – U (kishi) Shveytsariyadan. Her name is Ann – Uning (u kishining) ismi Ann. His name is Paul – Uning (u kishining) ismi Paul. As the examples show, in Uzbek sentences there is no strict indexing at gender (as in English) and one and the same pronoun can be used for both male and female. Structural discordance can appear in rendering compound and complex sentences. In another language the position of the main and subordinate clauses may be changed: I remember the time when we were children. – Men bolalik chog'imizni eslayman.

The complex sentence in English is rendered by a simple sentence in Uzbek because subordinate clause in the English sentence turns into an adjective + object phrase in Uzbek. Uzbek people often ask about someone's health: Sogligingiz yaxshimi? (=Is your health good? Is your health in a good condition?) [13]. But English people usually use one common and frequent question – How are you? In speech formulas of request the verb appears at the beginning in English sentences, as for Uzbek – at the end + negative form is used for producing polite request: Would you give me your book? – Kitobingizni berib turolmaysizmi? Could you stay here another day? – Bu erda yana bir kun qololmaysizmi?

CONCLUSION

As it is clear from the given above examples, the expression of politeness is rendered by verbs –could||, –would||, etc. in English, in Uzbek – by verbs in negative form: –yordam qilolmaysizmi||, –turolmaysizmi||, etc. These are also vivid examples of structural discordance of English and Uzbek set phrases. So, grammatical system of any language plays a great role in its functioning. To render appropriate meaningful content in a correct grammatical construction needs perfect knowledge and mastering grammatical peculiarities of both languages. The most difficult points in this aspect

are: syntactical structures, pronouns, article, gender, tenses and other grammatical categories [14-15].

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